

Search engines beyond search: questions for a critical knowledge infrastructure

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1. The dominance of search in interfaces to knowledge infrastructures

Search engines play a powerful role in ordering knowledge and in shaping interactions with data, sources or documents. They are central to many of the interfaces to contemporary knowledge infrastructures (Beaulieu, 2026a). The current dominance of ‘search’ has been well documented and various facets (relevance, optimization, ranking, bias) have been examined and refined in sophisticated ways. But as search engines become further embedded in layered knowledge infrastructures, it is all the more important to unearth how search shapes knowledge needs and how these needs are met (Beaulieu, 2026b).

A focus on the role of search in interfaces is especially helpful to start thinking differently about infrastructures, because of cultural associations of interfaces with possibility, potential, and dynamic realisation (Whitelaw, 2015)(Andrews & van Zundert, 2018). Many of us (especially in scholarly contexts) come to interfaces with the expectations that they are a site for activity. In contrast, infrastructures tend to fall into the background, to be experienced as neutral enablers. While there are very different takes on what it means to interact with an interface, there is an important contrast between how we experience interfaces and how we tend to experience infrastructures – as invisible, stable, monolithic, just ‘there’, consistently or intermittently. We feel much more engaged by interfaces, and experience our encounters as active and normative, often judging them as user-friendly or not. We are also increasingly becoming aware that interfaces read us, gathering data about our search terms, patterns, and even rhythms (Beaulieu & Leonelli, 2021), and profile us as users. This contrast is one of the elements that makes interfaces productive in rethinking knowledge for liveable futures. Interfaces and how they make search prominent can be rethought, so that changes can be made to how infrastructures constitutes routines, subjects and relations (Jensen & Morita, 2015; Povinelli, 2016).

2. Questioning assumptions about search

In this contribution, I want to share a number of questions to explore important assumptions of search engines: It is possible to imagine other functions for search engines, besides supporting retrieval? When is search good enough and how do we know what it is good for (Windhager et al., 2018)? What is a query (Katsogiannis-Meimarakis et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023), besides a suitable search term? Can a search engine succeed otherwise than through best match? Can assumptions be foregrounded so that search engines are more reflexive—at what cost and with which advantages? How do conversational interfaces increase the urgency of questioning these assumptions? These questions can spur new interactions and explorations across lines of work, connecting epistemology and design, ethics and computation, politics and indexing. The aim is to stimulation conversations about retrieval and recommendations, about diversity, inclusion, ignorance and to contribute to problematisations of bias, the political and moral economy of search engines, of retrieval and of reliability.

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3. Implementation of search as an opportunity for transformation

I will therefore consider how search is implemented in interfaces and sketch how to study and develop interfaces as specific encounters between systems and agents that are situated and that rely on particular conditions and skills. Interfaces that focus on search are too often unquestioned. While search engines have increasingly become able to accommodate a range of vocabularies, often in everyday vernacular and as part of an ongoing ‘conversation’, it remains that the use of terms must either correspond to articulated words, titles, or tags to be most effective, or be translatable to these, and that their *raison d’être* is retrieval, rather than say, discovery or exploration. Yet, there are many other potential implementations of search that could have important epistemological, ethical and political consequences. Redesigning interfaces can be a way to stop reproducing an architecture of universalism as a core element of systematicity, to question a mode of distributivity that foregrounds frictionless circulation of knowledge, and to open up the possibility of reflexivity.

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